

THE EFFECT OF PARTICULATE SiC REINFORCEMENT ON 2124 AL ALLOY

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ABSTRACT

A comparison has been made between an aluminium matrix composite with particulate SiC reinforcement, and the unreinforced matrix alloy, both made via a powder metallurgy route. The alloy, 2124 contains copper and magnesium as the main contributors to age hardening. A wide variety of techniques have been applied, and have revealed a number of differences from the expected precipitation sequence. Both materials precipitate both S' and θ' . GP zone precipitation is severely reduced in the composite. S' is also reduced but to a lesser extent, with dislocations acting as nucleation sites. The acceleration of aging, and the increased dislocation density around the reinforcement in the composite is confirmed.

INTRODUCTION

For the past few decades there has been a quest for materials with high specific strength and toughness for aerospace applications. Efforts have been made to improve traditional aluminium alloys such as the age hardening Al-Cu-Mg alloy 2024. The common impurities iron and silicon were reduced and the new alloy was designated 2124. The main age hardening precipitate in this alloy is S' and it also contains $Al_{20}Cu_2Mn_3$ as a grain refiner, and some intermetallics containing iron, which is still present as an impurity [1].

Metal matrix composites gave further improvements in the specific properties of these alloys, particularly 2124, 6061, and 8090. SiC is a common reinforcement for aluminium alloys. Although the density is increased by the addition of SiC, this is offset by the improvement in mechanical properties achieved.

2124-SiC composites are usually made by a powder metallurgy route, avoiding use of liquid metal which would produce a brittle reaction zone of Al_4C_3 around the reinforcement. An extensive study of the phases observed in such a composite was published in 1986 and showed S' to be the age hardening phase, with stable S at grain and subgrain boundaries [2]. The same intermetallics containing Mn and Fe were seen as in the unreinforced alloy, and also MgO from the surface of the powder used to make the alloy.

A widely reported effect of the addition of reinforcement is the acceleration of the aging process. This is thought to be due to an increased dislocation density around the reinforcement, arising from punching of dislocations during quenching, due to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion between the matrix and reinforcement. These dislocations act as potent nucleation sites, and also provide rapid routes for pipe diffusion. [3, 4, 5]. They have also been seen forming during in situ heating and cooling experiments in the TEM [6].

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

MATERIALS

In this study a powder metallurgy composite made by BP (now AMC Ltd) was compared with an unreinforced 2124 alloy made by a powder metallurgy route at Imperial College. The composite contained 20 vol% SiC particles, nominally $3\mu\text{m}$ in size.

Both materials were solution heat treated for one hour at 505°C , and quenched into polymer glycol quenchant. Samples were then either stored in a freezer for examination in the as-quenched state, or aged for intervals of one hour, up to eight hours at 130°C , 150°C , or 180°C . All results reported here are from samples aged at 180°C , and detailed examination has been carried out on samples as-quenched, and after 1, 5 and 8 hours of aging.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The aging of the materials was monitored by hardness measurements. Ten readings were taken from each sample using a 10kg weight. The mean of these readings is taken as the hardness and the standard deviation as the error.

Differential scanning calorimetry was used to examine the kinetics of aging of the as-quenched sample. Samples were heated at $20^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in a Stanton Redcroft DSC 1500 with a high sensitivity head. Samples were heated in an argon atmosphere to avoid oxidation and a super-pure aluminium reference was employed. The baseline was found not to be constant between samples, so each sample was heated twice in order to get a sample specific base line. The second run (the baseline) was subtracted from the first (experimental line) to reveal the enthalpy peaks of the reactions. The curves were normalised by dividing by the weight of 2124 alloy in the sample. For the unreinforced material this was simply the weight of the sample, but for the composite it was the weight of the sample multiplied by $83/100$.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to examine the major phases present in each sample. Samples were prepared by mechanical polishing and diffraction experiments were carried out using a Phillips PW1710 diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation (wavelength 1.54\AA), taking readings for 1 second every 0.04° , between $2\theta=10^\circ$ and $2\theta=90^\circ$

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to reveal the detailed microstructure of the samples. Samples were examined in a JEOL 2000FX microscope operating at 200kV, in bright field (BF), dark field (DF) and selected area diffraction (SAD) modes. Intermetallic phases were identified by EDX analysis

RESULTS

HARDNESS

Figure 1: Variation of hardness with time at 180°C

Both materials experience an initial increase, followed by a drop, and a further increase to peak hardness. The unreinforced alloy undergoes a total increase in hardness of around 47 from the as-quenched value to the peak, whereas the composite hardness increases by only 27 Hv.

AS-QUENCHED

DSC

In figure 2a the composite was tested immediately after quenching, whereas the sample in 2b had been stored in a freezer prior to testing. The composite and the unreinforced material show a similar range of reactions in figure 2a. There is an initial exothermic peak attributed to GP zone precipitation, followed by a small endotherm as some dissolve. This is followed by large peak corresponding to precipitation of S'. Figure 2b shows that for samples stored in the freezer the GP zone precipitation peak is missing, but the dissolution peak is still evident, indicating that GP zones form during storage.

The sizes and peak temperatures of the reactions are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2a: DSC curves from the unreinforced alloy and the freshly quenched composite

Figure 2b: DSC curve from the composite after storage in a freezer

Table 1: Peak sizes and temperatures from DSC curves of various samples

Reaction	Unreinforced		Fresh composite		Stored composite	
	Enthalpy	Peak T	Enthalpy	Peak T	Enthalpy	Peak T
GP pptn	-23	66	-7	74	0	-
GP dissn	8	224	3	225	4	226
S' pptn	27	284	-13	285	-12	291

XRD

XRD results from both materials are shown in the as-quenched state in figure 3. The as-quenched unreinforced material was shown to contain aluminium with a small trace of retained θ . The composite showed aluminium, retained θ and SiC. The SiC was mainly β phase, but commercial SiC usually contains a number of isomorphs. A number of other peaks were identified by matching against results from a sample of commercial SiC. A few peaks remain unidentified.

Figure 3: XRD patterns from both materials as-quenched

TEM

After solution heat treatment and quenching the unreinforced alloy shows retained θ and an aluminium based Mn-Cu intermetallic, identified by EDX analysis (figure 4). Transmission electron microscopy of the composite shows a large number of small flakes of SiC of less than $1\mu\text{m}$ in size in addition to the $3\mu\text{m}$ particles. Other phases seen are retained θ and manganese copper containing intermetallics, which have a rounder shape (figure 5). Also a high dislocation density is seen close to the SiC (figure 6).

Figure 4: As-quenched unreinforced alloy

Figure 5: As-quenched composite

Figure 6: Dislocations resulting from quenching
a: Bright field

b: Dark field

AGING

XRD

The XRD traces of both materials are shown in figure 7. S' appears in both materials after only one hour and remains throughout the eight hours of aging. No additional phases are detected during the aging. The experiment was designed only for identification of major phases, so detailed analysis of lattice parameters of aging phases or volume fractions of phases has not been carried out.

Figure 7: XRD results after 8 hours aging

TEM

After 1 hour the unreinforced alloy shows faint S' in 100 diffraction patterns (figure 8) which is also clearly visible as rods in the dark field image after 5 hours of aging (figure 9). However after 8 hours θ' spots as well as S' are observed in 100 and 110 diffraction patterns (figure 10). The S' is present as corrugated sheets as well as rods (figure 11). The composite after 1 hour aging shows faint S' spots in 100 diffraction patterns. This is clearly visible after 5 hours aging, together with some θ' (figure 12). The S' can be seen nucleated on dislocations in bright field images (figure 13).

After 8 hours strong S' is observed together with θ' in 100 diffraction patterns (figure 14). There is a large amount of dislocation nucleated S', particularly close to the SiC where a high dislocation density was seen in the as-quenched state (figure 15).

Figure 8 : 100 diffraction pattern after 1 hour aging showing faint S' crosses

Figure 9a: 100 diffraction pattern after 5 hours aging

Figure 9b: Dark field from S' crosses, showing rods of S' in the matrix

Figure 10a (left): 100 diffraction pattern after 8 hours aging showing S' between matrix spots and θ' through spots

Figure 10b (centre): 110 diffraction pattern after 8 hours aging

Figure 11 (right): Bright field after 8 hours aging showing corrugated sheets of S' and heavy matrix coverage

Figure 12: 100 diffraction pattern of composite after 5 hours aging showing θ' in addition to S'

Figure 13: Bright field of composite after 5 hours aging showing S' nucleated on dislocations

Figure 14: 100 diffraction pattern of composite after 8 hours aging showing S' and θ'

Figure 15: Bright field of composite after 8 hours aging showing S' nucleated on dislocations

DISCUSSION

The acceleration of precipitation hardening in the composite is confirmed by this study. Peak hardness is reached in approximately 3 hours in the composite, but takes 8 hours in the unreinforced alloy. The excess dislocations seen in the composite act as potent nucleation sites for S' , increasing the precipitation kinetics.

The S' precipitation peak temperature is unchanged by the addition of SiC reinforcement, and the

temperature of GP zone precipitation is increased. This is consistent with the results of Papazian, who found that powder metallurgy production of unreinforced 2124 gave a reduction in peak temperatures compared to the standard wrought production route but there was no further reduction on addition of reinforcement.

The GP precipitation peak is missing entirely in the composite stored in the freezer, although the subsequent endothermic dissolution peak is present, and approximately the same size as that in the fresh composite. The enthalpy of S' precipitation is also slightly reduced after the composite has been stored. This implies that even at very low temperatures the composite is undergoing GP zone precipitation.

The enthalpy of GP zone precipitation is smaller in the freshly quenched composite than the unreinforced material. The subsequent small endotherm, attributed to partial dissolution of GP zones, is in the same ratio to the exotherm in both the unreinforced alloy and the freshly quenched composite. The S' precipitation peak is also reduced in magnitude in the composite, but the ratio of S' formed : GP zones formed is greater in the composite than the unreinforced alloy. This reduction in the quantity of S' formed in the composite accounts for the smaller increases in hardness seen in the composite during artificial aging.

The concentration of vacancies has a major effect on the formation of GP zones. The reduction in enthalpy of GP zone formation in the composite has been attributed by Papazian to dislocations formed during quenching acting as vacancy sinks, so reducing the concentration of vacancies. The reduced number of GP zones forces nucleation of S' on dislocations in the composite, as seen in TEM

The reduction in S' forming may be due to Mg depletion in the matrix. An alloy of this composition should age entirely through formation of S', but it was found that θ' was also forming in both the unreinforced material and the composite. This suggests the loss of magnesium to MgO as a result of powder processing in both materials, and an additional loss in the composite to a reaction with the SiC. This explains both the reduction in enthalpy of S' formation and in the smaller hardness increment in the composite.

SUMMARY

The acceleration of age hardening in 2124 due to the addition of reinforcement is confirmed.

The presence of a high dislocation density around SiC reinforcement particles is also confirmed.

Unreinforced 2124 produced by a powder metallurgy route and 2124 with SiC reinforcement have been shown to form both S' and θ' during age hardening.

The amount of GP zones formed is reduced in the composite. This attributed to dislocations acting as vacancy sinks and reducing the number of nucleation sites.

The amount of S' formed is also reduced in the composite, but to a lesser extent. S' is nucleated on dislocations.

It is suggested that MgO may be formed during production of alloys from powder, moving the alloy into the Al+S'+ θ' phase field and reducing the amount of S' formed. In the composite the amount of Mg may be further reduced by the formation of Mg₂Si at the matrix-SiC interface

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